

Activity assay for ALK2 (ACVR1) GS loop mutations.

Aim: the goal of the assay was to observe the phosphorylation of SMAD1 by ALK2 in the presence of ACVR2 by mass spec and to observe the phosphorylation on ALK2 for differences to the wild type protein.

Method:

The following incubations were set up using ACVR1Z c103 and c104 containing the following GS loop mutations:

WT: SMTTINVGDSTLADLLDHSCTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSWQGENVAVKIF...
103: SMTTINVGDSTLADLLDHA^ACTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSWQGENVAVKIF...
104: SMTTINVGDSTLADLLDHS^AASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSWQGENVAVKIF...

Proteins were thawed from storage at -80°C and concentrations assessed by Nano drop.

From the concentrations, appropriate dilutions were calculated to get a final concentration of 40 µM for all proteins in a reaction mix of 100 µL (volume made up with 50mM HEPES, 300mM NaCl pH7.5).

Insufficient ACVR1 wild type was present to do a proper negative control however the positive control was just possible at slightly lower concentrations.

A 'master mix' containing ATP, ions and DTT was made up and added to activate the reaction at the start of the experiment.

protein	absorbance	ext. coef.	concentration	amount for 40uM in 100ul.
A1 wild type	3.026	58900	51.37521222	77.85855915
A1 c103	13.55	58900	230.0509338	17.38745387
A1 c104	16.57	58900	281.3242784	14.21846711
ACVR2A	22.8	51900	439.3063584	9.105263158
BMPR2A	19.35	46870	412.8440367	9.688888889
SMAD1	4.36	35410	123.1290596	32.48623853

Assessment of concentrations of samples by spectroscopy and the dilution needed in 100ul for the correct concentration in the final mix.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
A1 76	78	78									
A1 103			17	17				17			
A1 104					14	14			14		
ACVR2A	9		9		9					9	
BMP2A		10		10		10					10
SMAD1	32	32	32	32	32	32	32				
Master Mix	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Buffer	-23	-24	38	37	41	40	64	79	82	87	86

Plate layout for the reactions including volumes needed of each component.

	rxn vol 100
Master mix	10 rxn
ATP	2.5
DTT (1M)	2.5
Mg	25
Mn	10
(all at 100mM)	40

Concentrations needed for the master activating mix.

plate 1		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	A1_76 A2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
B	A1_76 B2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
C	A1 103 A2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
D	A1 103 B2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
E	A1 104 A2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
F	A1 104 B2	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
G	S ONLY	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
H	103 ONLY	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
plate 2													
A	104 ONLY	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
B	A2 ONLY	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
C	B2 ONLY	0s	30s	1min	90s	2min	3min	4min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min
D	30 min	A1_76 A2	A1_76 B2	A1 103 A2	A1 103 B2	A1 104 A2	A1 104 B2	S ONLY	103 ONLY	104 ONLY	A2 ONLY	B2 ONLY	
		insufficient protein for A1_76 alone.											

Plate layout for the reactions run on the mass spec showing plate name and well position for identification of raw data.

Reactions were set up in a 96 well plate, the plate was spun to ensure thorough mixing before the reaction was started by the addition of master mix. 1 μ L of reaction mixture was extracted from each experimental condition simultaneously using a 12 channel pipette at specific time points (0, 30s, 1min, 90s, 2min, 3min, 4min, 5min, 10min, 15min, 20min, 25min and 30min) and the reaction quenched with acid in 60 μ L Mass Spec running buffer (water with 0.1% formic acid).

Mass spec analysis:

Intact mass was determined using a QTOF mass spectrometer. A C3 cartridge was used for HPLC prior to ionisation.

The resulting chromatogram was used to extract the appropriate spectra corresponding to protein elution peak from the C3 column. All spectra were extracted simultaneously. Deconvolution was undertaken between 10kDa and 50kDa across a limited m/z range of 600 – 3000.

Data was exported with a peak intensity for every Dalton of the deconvoluted spectra. The data was plotted using Excell. The Raw data can be found on Zenodo.

Results:

Mass spec traces focused on SMAD1 mass looking at phosphorylation at 0min (blue) and 25min (green) showing the wild type has increased phosphorylation occupancy compared to the mutants.

Mass spec traces focused on ACVR1/ALK2 mass looking at phosphorylation at 0min (blue) and 25min (green) showing the wild type has increased phosphorylation occupancy compared to the mutants however it is unclear if this is due to a loss of a phosphorylation site or a change in phosphorylation pattern. It is known that there are up to 8 phosphorylation sites possible so the reduction of observable phosphorylation's in the GS loop mutants does not conclusively tell us what is going on.